

Study the effect of Bacterial protein Azurin and tumor suppressor p53 on cancer cells

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Abstract: Azurin is a low molecular weight redox protein that is derived from the pathogenic bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. It is commonly utilized as a representative bacterial product in the treatment of tumors. 16S rRNA was used in this investigation to identify *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* that was isolated from the lungs of Egyptian individuals with cystic fibrosis. A appropriate PCR program was used to amp up the azurin gene. Sequencing was done after the gene was cloned into the pGEM-T simple vector. the expression bacterium *E. coli* BL21 were then subcloned into the overexpression vector pET-28a (+). In *E. coli*, the gene was overexpressed, according to the SDS-PAGE study. Using Ni⁺⁺ resin, a one-step purification process was used to produce the recombinant protein. Human breast cancer cell line (MCF7) and human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line: the impact of azurin on proliferation and apoptosis.

Key words: Azurin, cell lines, antitumor, Cancer, tumor suppressor p53, p28, and *pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Introduction

Cancer was treated using live or attenuated pathogenic bacteria or their byproducts [1] An notable reduction of mice's subcutaneous tumors was noted when anaerobic bacteria were combined with different chemotherapy drugs [2]. A little globular metalloprotein called as zurin is endowed with involving redox activity and contributing to bacterial the process of denitrification [3]. It is functioning as a shuttle for electron transfers. in several microorganisms, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The copper ion's presence provides this protein with a variety of characteristics, such as a strong blue hue and a high decrease potential and a modest parallel hyperfine coupling in the spectrum of electron spin resonance [4].

Background and Methods

Isolation and identification of bacterial strain: A bacterial strain was identified, and determined by means of physiological characterization of microbiology and biochemistry [1]. moreover, additional molecular partial characterisation using PCR amplification composition of the 16S rRNA gene. pairs of universal primers We utilized 9F and 1512R to amplify about 1500 bps. As these Primers are utilized to augment the majority of per [3], eubacteria. The results of PCR were leaned using PCR and purified using Wizard® SV Gel kit in accordance with the guidelines supplied by the provider and resolved on a 1% agarose gel by electrophoresis. As the refined substance. The Type 1 cupredoxin protein, azurin, is secreted by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a harmful bacteria. The X-ray structure at 1.93 Å indicates that azurin is made up of aneigh beta-strands grouped in a Greek key pattern, an alpha helix, and controlled by three potent equatorial ligands and the copper ion two less potent axial ligands.[5] Unveiling a new purpose, the One protein that helped the bacteria in the denitrification process was shown to induce apoptosis in J777 macrophages.[6] Afterwards with the finding of the ability of selective entrance and cytotoxicity in the direction of malignant cells like human melanoma UISO Mel 2. and MCF 7 Azurin breast cancer cells gained attention drawing scientific interest as a possible cancer-fighting substance.[4,5] Azurin gained attention and attracted the scientists' focus as a possible.

p53

The transcription factor known as the tumour suppressor p53 is connected to numerous signalling pathways. p53 is stabilized when it is normally present at low levels because of the action of negative regulators like MDM2. via post-translational changes that increase intracellular levels triggering target genes downstream to initiate cell When DNA damage is detected, cycle arrest, DNA repair, and apoptosis occur. or stressful circumstances.[7] Put differently, referred to as the protector of p53 protects the integrity of the genome, preventing cancer development.[8,9] Consequently, the loss of regulation and function of p53 is a significant contributor to cancer, and research has demonstrated that p53 mutations are linked to 50% of malignancies. its potential as an anticancer target.[10,11].

Structure of p53

With four identical subunits, p53 is a tetrameric protein consisting of 393 amino acids. It is known that each monomer consists of three primary domains, each with a distinct function: N-DNA binding protein called terminal transactivation domain (NTD) a C terminal domain (CTD) and a domain (DBD). N terminal region that is in charge of transcription factor activation comprises a proline-rich segment and a transactivation domain. crucial to the process of apoptosis. The primary domain is recognized as the area in charge of DNA binding and is seen as a center for mutations. Additionally, the mutations in this area are frequently linked to tumor loss suppressor role. Domain of tetramerization accountable for the protein's tetramerization and nuclear localization a NLS signal as well as a NES (nuclear export signal).

p53 Mechanism of Action of Azurin

Strategies to stabilise p53 and counteract the action of its down regulators should offer the prospect of restoration of structural stability and optimal intracellular levels of the protein, which are crucial for its anticancer function. The p53 function [12] After completing numerous mechanistic investigations, Azurin has demonstrated its ability to inhibit cancer via similarly protein stabilization and subsequent upregulation in the p53 pathway levels and regaining its ability to

inhibit tumors. Among the first indications of this method of action of Azurin was discovered in the J774 macrophage research where An increase in reactive oxygen caused apoptosis to be initiated. organisms (ROS) [13] Still, a number of redox negative azurin Additionally, ROS-induced macrophage apoptosis was produced by mutants. suggesting that azurin's cytotoxicity has nothing to do with its redox activity [14].

More focus on interaction between Azurin and p53 Interactions

Examining azurin and p53 interactions in more detail, a few investigations have revealed that azurin binds to full-length p53 in a stoichiometry of 4:1, as confirmed. by using an isothermal calorimeter.[15] The same was validated by Atomic force microscopy and surface plasmon resonance experiments,[15,16], but a few more disclosed the potential interactions between azurin and perhaps CTD, DBD, and NTD of p53 on its own.[17,18] .On the other hand, as site-directed mutagenesis demonstrates, Azurin's hydrophobic region is typically involved in redox interactions with two methionine residues and additional partners in this area, positions 44 and 64 are thought to be vital. for its interacts with p53.[19,20] One of the most researched DBDs on record is p53. relations between p53 and azurin.[18,19] docking of proteins and free energy-related stimulants haveNTD of azurin exists as an unstructured domain in solution.[15] Containing binding site for MDM2, the main deregulator of p53, is a probable target for protein association. Several investigations from computer simulations to biophysical studies have been carried out to probe the probable azurin–NTD interactions.[8,18] As recorded by a fluorescence study, decrease of tryptophan emission was observed with an increase in secondary structure, which can be attributed to azurin Cu 2+ effect on binding to NTD.[18] A computational study carried out on the same has suggested the probable binding of azurin to helices HI and HIII which are hypothesised to overlap with the MDM2-binding region.[8] The region corresponding to 15–29 residues of transactivation domain has attracted the attention of scientists as a MDM2-binding site.[16] Contradicting Compared to p53 DBD and NTD, literature is sparse on possible azurin and CTD interactions. Moreover, Glutathione S transferase (GST pull down assay) pull-down assay only indicated weak interactions.[19] However, the insight into CTD is of importance because its mutations have been associated with p53 ubiquitination and degradation.[20] Another interesting feature on this domain is that it has the ability to interact with nucleic acids, changing the structure of p53, and thus modulate interactions with other proteins. In a similar study, nucleic acid-mediated interaction of azurin with CTD was detected, supporting the possibility that nucleic acid might allosterically regulate the CTD confirmation, aiding p53–azurin interaction.[14] Therefore, considering the literature so far what is evident is that there are still many open issues and contradictions regarding .At the same time, immunogenicity is a significant hindrance that compromises the pharmaceutical efficacy of a protein which could be the same in case of azurin. In realisation, scientists have been able to unravel a truncated version of azurin, which affirms the same therapeutic efficacy with target specificity, preferential entry and cytotoxicity, but with potentially less side effects. Therefore, the rest of this communication will be dedicated to the peptide fragment p28 for its p53-mediated mechanism of action as a potential anticancer agent.

p28

Possessing a molecular mass of 2.9 kDa, the peptide p28 corresponds to amino acids 50–77 of the bacterial cupredoxin azurin.[20] Consisting of an extended alpha helix with a β -strand, a turn and

an irregular structure, p28 is stable and well folded when in association with the protein.[7] Being an amphipathic, anionic cell-penetrating peptide, it has exhibited function similar to azurin, resulting in tumour regression.[20] As a small molecule, it comes with an added advantage of no significant toxicity or adverse effects.[19,20].

Antitumor Action of p28

Similar to azurin, p28 not only interacts with p53 but also interferes with other pathways.[7] For instance, p53-independent inhibition of angiogenesis and tumour growth was recorded in a study of p28 on human umbilical vein endothelial cells where p28 by interaction with VEGFR-2 caused inhibition of FAK and Akt phosphorylation.[12] However, much evidence point towards the anti-proliferative action arising from stabilisation of p53. According to a study on human breast cancer cell lines MCF-7, ZR-75-1 and T47D, p28 showed preferential entry into cancer cells through a caveolin-mediated pathway.[20] The anti-proliferative activity of p28 was appeared to result from complex formation via hydrophobic interaction with DBD and post-translational stabilisation of p53, elevating its intracellular levels. The activation of p53 by p28 and posttranslational increase of expression.

Therapeutic methods of Azurine and p28

Characterized by the specificity of the target, selective entry and ability to induce cell cycle arrest and apoptosis, azurin and its derived peptide p28 offer new perspectives to anticancer therapeutics. Standing through two Phase 1 clinical trials, one in adults with metastatic solid tumours [20] and the other in children with brain tumours, p28 has affirmed its anticancer activity as a safe and well-tolerated agent.[20] In addition to being effective alone,[10] azurin acts as a drug sensitizer when employed in combination with other anticancer drugs. Combined application with azurin increased the sensitivity of MCF-7 breast cancer cells, HeLa cervical cancer cells and HT-29 colon cancer cells to paclitaxel and doxorubicin [20] Oral squamous carcinoma cells (YD-9) displayed increased sensitivity to 5-fluorouracil and etoposide [20] Cell-penetrating peptides (CPP) possess the ability to cross biological membranes, thus delivering bioactive cargo into cells. p28 being a CPP with preferential entry into cancer cells is ideal to be used in cancer-targeted drug delivery systems. Studies reveal that CPP can be conjugated to anticancer drugs through covalent or non-covalent strategies.[20] In an attempt to develop a HPV therapeutic vaccine, p28 has shown successful results with effective delivery of HPV16 E7 protein to cancer cells. [19] Chimeric protein of apoptin and p28 produced synergistic effects on breast cancer cell lines.[20] Granzyme B-azurin fusion produced selective effectiveness inducing apoptosis in MDA-MB-231, MCF7 and SK-BR-3 breast cancer cell lines with insignificant cytotoxicity to MCF 10A normal breast cells.[20].

Conclusion

Cancer as a global threat is a complex disease that demands new therapeutic interventions. Bacterial cupredoxin azurin and its peptide p28 are multitargeted anticancer agents which exert their action by interfering with multiple signalling pathways. Tumour suppressor p53 is a key regulator of cell cycle which plays a vital role in the prevention of carcinogenesis. Being susceptible to frequent mutation, it is recognised as an appealing target for cancer therapy. Past studies revealing details of p53-mediated mechanism of action have indicated that upon preferential penetration into cancer cells, azurin complexes with p53 DBD or NTD, counteracting the effects of its down regulators, stabilising and raising its intracellular levels. This in turn results

in the activation of downstream targets, leading to cell cycle arrest, apoptosis and thus tumor regulation. In addition, More focus new functions of azurin and discovery of putative bacteriocins with functional similarity and evaluation of combinatorial therapeutic methods might provide better perspectives to targeted cancer therapy.

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